

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Evaluation of Nonlinearities in a Diode Clipper Circuit based on Wave Digital Filters

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Abstract

This thesis examines the method of virtual analog modeling known as wave digital filters, and specifically its application in adequately capturing the behavior of nonlinear audio circuits. An overview of various methods of virtual analog modeling are presented, as well as other common approaches to nonlinear system identification. In order to evaluate the wave digital filters, we construct a Python library with various circuit elements and circuit classes. We focus on evaluating the approximation of a diode clipper, a common nonlinear circuit used in audio signal processing. In the evaluation, we compare the frequency response of our wave digital model and SPICE simulations of the same circuit. We make such comparisons at several sample rates and parameter changes. We further perform transient analysis and examine the harmonics added by the circuit and measure the amount of total harmonic distortion introduced, at multiple sample rates and parameter changes. We lastly process the clipper with a swept sine wave across all frequencies, which is convolved with an inverse filter of the sweep, and is then used to calculate a transfer function of the system that accounts for the nonlinear behavior.

Keywords: virtual analog modeling, wave digital filters, diode clipper, audio signal processing, digital signal processing, nonlinear signal processing

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Virtual analog modeling is the task of replicating the behavior of analog circuits in the digital domain. As digital technologies continue to advance, analog technologies of the days before digital are becoming less and less common. However, this is what drives the pursuit of 'vintage' recording gear. Musicians and engineers are very fond of the tools used by the pioneers of analog audio effects, and for good reason. The phrase 'analog warmth' is often found in analog modeled plugin marketing campaigns, because electronic audio equipment often does have nonlinearities that can saturate or distort the signals, providing a unique tone that is difficult to replicate digitally. Nowadays, this vintage gear can often be difficult to find or build, or if not, can be prohibitively expensive. Providing digital software emulations of analog gear that account for all their timbral nuances makes this search for vintage gear much less difficult.

For these reasons, the recreation of analog audio effects circuits in the digital domain has long been of great interest to audio engineers and plugin developers.

While imitating the behavior of linear time invariant systems has yielded many great results for the field of digital audio signal processing, adequately modeling the behavior of nonlinear circuits has proven to be a far more difficult task.

Most efforts to model analog circuits can be considered either ‘white-box’ or ‘black-box’. In white box approaches, engineers attempt to recreate the internal workings of the system by modeling all of its internal components. Common examples of white box modeling include state space methods, physical modeling, and wave digital filters.

Black box approaches on the other hand, simply measure outputs compared to the inputs and seek to model the system based on this information. Common examples of black box approaches include neural networks and machine learning, Volterra Series, and the swept sine method.

Most audio systems must be able to perform in real time situations, which places a significant constraint on the methods of modeling. This is a key reason we have elected to use the wave digital filter method.

1.2 Objectives

In this report, we seek to prove the viability of the wave digital filter analog modeling technique. We aim to do so by demonstrating its accuracy, speed, and capability in recreating the nonlinear behavior of an analog diode clipper circuit.

1.3 Structure of the Report

This paper is structured as follows: Chapter 2 will present the state of the art of nonlinear digital signal processing and wave digital filters, Chapter 3 will outline the methodology used in this thesis to gain our results, Chapter 4 will present the results, and Chapter 5 will discuss the results and focus on possible areas of future work in this field.

Chapter 2

State Of the Art

2.1 Nonlinear Systems

Many audio signal processing systems fall under the category of linear & timeinvariant systems. A linear system is one that abides by the superposition principle, which states that a function must satisfy the properties of additivity:

$$F(x_1 + x_2) = F(x_1) + F(x_2) \quad (2.1)$$

And homogeneity:

$$F(a * x) = a * F(x) \quad (2.2)$$

for scalar a

A time-invariant system is one whose output is delayed by the same amount as when the input is delayed, and vice versa.

Linear time-invariant systems have been of great interest thanks to several unique properties. The fact that they can be characterized entirely by the system's impulse response is quite advantageous. Consequently, if one knows the impulse response of a system, they can compute the output for any input using convolution. This additionally allows for the relatively straightforward construction of these systems

as finite impulse response filters and infinite impulse response filters (FIRs and IIRs). [1] These techniques laid the groundwork for digital audio signal processing, and have been extensively employed for the development of several classes of audio signal processing effects. Audio effects that are linear time-invariant are reverb, filter, and delay. Linear time-variant audio effects include the chorus, flanger, phaser, tremolo, and vibrato. The most common examples of audio effects that are nonlinear and time-invariant are compression and saturation/distortion. [2] This means that outputs of compression and distortion are delayed by the same amount as a delayed input, but that they do not adhere to the superposition principle (equations 2.1 and 2.2). Consequently, the system has a nonlinear transfer function and cannot be characterized by an impulse response, and its outputs cannot be determined with convolution.

There has historically been a great deal of interest in replicating nonlinear systems in the digital domain, especially within the context of audio, as the unique character of analog compression and distortion systems is highly sought after. This is owed to many reasons, in part due to nostalgia for the recording tools and effects used prior to the digital age of audio. But also because many of these analog effects units are difficult to find if not excessively costly. Creating an accurate digital version that can run on any capable computer would either remove or significantly lower the barrier of entry to using these devices.

An accurate method of representing these systems must consider real time streaming audio applications, which places a significant restraint on the computational complexity. Achieving nonlinear transfer functions digitally has been a huge area of audio signal processing research for these reasons.

2.2 Nonlinear System Identification Techniques

The approaches to modeling nonlinear systems generally include white box modeling and black box modeling. A white box model attempts to recreate the internal behavior of the system by modeling its components. A black box model will sim-

ply take measurements of inputs and outputs and attempt to mimic the internal behavior.

2.2.1 Black box modeling

Black box modeling of nonlinear systems is a common approach, and is advantageous in that no prior knowledge of the system or its internal workings is required. The model is created by taking measurements of how the system responds to different inputs, and calculating the behavior based on their outputs. Some of the most notable examples of black box models are neural networks and machine learning, Volterra series, and the swept sine method.

Volterra Series

This method is named after Vita Volterra, the Italian mathematician who first applied it to model the behavior of nonlinear ordinary differential equations in 1887.[3] The Volterra Series is similar to the Taylor Series, but differs in that it has a memory effect, which makes it more effective at calculating distortion at high frequencies.

The discrete time Volterra Series is defined by the summation equation:

$$y(n) = \sum_{i=0}^n h(\tau_i) \cdot x(n - \tau_i) \quad (2.3)$$

n: time index, $h(\tau)$: impulse response

Norbert Wiener was later the first to use the Volterra Series in the context of nonlinear circuit analysis in 1942. Hammerstein-Wiener models refer to a classification of nonlinear system identification based on Wiener's application of the Volterra Series to circuit analysis. A Hammerstein model contains a nonlinearity block followed by a linear filter and is typically done in parallel. The Wiener model is quite similar, the lone difference being the linear filter precedes the nonlinearity. [3]

Machine Learning

Machine learning has become an extremely popular method of virtual analog modeling. However, using it for the simulation of nonlinear effects remains a difficult task. In general, a large amount of training data is required to adequately capture the system's behavior. In addition, having these models run at audio rates is another difficult task. Notable efforts tackling these issues include Steinmetz and Reiss's Steerable discovery of neural audio effects [4], which allows a user to input a dry sound and a processed sound, and the network will 'learn' the effect. Another notable example is the RTNeural framework developed in [5], which has addressed the speed needs for running machine learning models in real time applications. Native Instruments has also recently released a landmark machine learning audio effects system in Guitar Rig 6, for which they developed cutting edge algorithms to simulate guitar pedals and amplifiers. [6]

Swept Sine Method

Recording the response of a system to a swept sine has long been used in audio signal processing. It was employed initially to determine frequency responses and impulse responses of rooms, and later in identifying nonlinear systems as well. [7]

A sine sweep can be input to a nonlinear system, and its output used to measure a multidimensional impulse response of the nonlinear system. This is done by creating an inverse filter of the sine sweep, and convolving the system's output with the inverse filter. [8]

One is then able to use this convolved signal to understand and visualize the behavior of higher order harmonics when inputs are fed into the nonlinear system. The result is similar to the system's Volterra Series.

2.2.2 White Box Modeling

White box modeling of nonlinear systems is advantageous because it takes into account the actual internal structure of the system. Doing so accurately preserves

the underlying structure and yields highly precise results. Examples of white box modeling include physical modeling, state space representations and wave digital filters.

Physical Modeling

Physical modeling of circuits typically entails deriving a transfer function in the s domain and converting it to the digital domain, generally via the bilinear transform. There exist an abundance of resources on physical modeling of circuits and is the most common method of circuit discretization. It does have its limitations, however, as if one wishes to change an individual component of the circuit, one must recompute the entire system's transfer function. This being said, the technique does consistently yield strong results and has been a top area of research for discretizing audio effect circuits. [9].

State Space Representations

State space representations refer to a methodology of converting the time domain behavior of a system into sets of input-output relationships based on differential or difference equations, using state variables. State variables denote the smallest set of system variables that can be used to describe the entirety of the system's state at any moment. This technique has proven very successful in modeling nonlinear and time variant systems and is another quite common approach. Often times solutions to the state space equations must be solved iteratively, which is unsuitable for real time applications. However, developments in simplifying these expressions for use have proliferated, such as the nodal NK method proposed in [10].

2.3 Wave Digital Filters

Wave digital filters were initially developed in the 1970s, and first covered extensively in a seminal work in 1986 by Alfred Fettweis. [11] The formalism was first utilized in the context of audio processing when Julius Smith realized the connection to his digital waveguide modeling. [12]

Wave digital filters are similar to the method of physical modeling, differing in that they are constructed by discretizing individual circuit elements, as opposed to systems' entire transfer functions. This is what allows such modularity; if one wished to change an individual element of a circuit, they would need to recompute the entire transfer function, but with wave digital filters they can simply replace that specific element and the system would run with no issues. Local discretization of components also allows wave digital filters to retain the energetic properties of the filter being modeled, and leads to strong accuracy and stability in simulations [11] [13].

Because the wave digital filter formalism was not initially developed with audio circuits in mind, many common components in audio circuits were exceedingly difficult, if not impossible to model. This is because they were at first limited to strictly ladder and lattice circuit topologies. This restriction excluded elements like operational amplifiers, transistors, and systems with multiple nonlinearities. However, recent advancements with R -type adaptors in wave digital filter theory have continued to increase the types of circuits that can be represented in this manner [14].

By modeling the circuit itself, wave digital filters retain its physical structure, and provide faithful recreations of it. The circuit is realized digitally by converting it into a (generally) binary connection tree ¹, an efficient graph system for implementing wave digital filters. The connection tree entails classifying one of the system's elements as the 'root', and allowing the rest of the components to organize themselves below as a tree. As such, the root has no upward facing port. Other elements that comprise a connection tree are the leaves - elements that have one upward facing port and no downward facing ports, and adaptors - which have one upward facing port and one or more ports facing downward [13].

A digital filter can only be realizable if it satisfies two conditions. The first is that it can be arranged into a series of simple operations such as summers, multipliers, and reads and writes to delay registers. The second is that it cannot contain any delay

¹The SPQR connection tree is typically used for circuits with complicated topologies

free loops in its signal path, i.e a signal cannot follow a closed path that contains no delays. In the connection tree framework, all delay free loops originate in upward facing ports. In order to ensure a realizable digital filter, these delay free loops at upward facing ports must be eliminated, or 'adapted'.

A central concept to wave digital filters is the notion of a 'port'. A network port is a pair of terminals (one negative and one positive) connected to an electrical element. In the Kirchoff domain, the port is specified by its port voltage (the voltage drop between the positive terminal to the negative) and its port current (the current flowing into the positive terminal). In the wave digital domain, the port is represented with an incident wave, a reflected wave, and a free variable port resistance which parametrizes these waves [11].

The incident wave uses the variable a , and is defined as:

$$a(t) = v(t) + i(t)R_p \quad (2.4)$$

Where v = voltage, i = current, and R_p = port resistance. The reflected wave uses the variable b , and is defined as:

$$b(t) = v(t) - i(t)R_p \quad (2.5)$$

Thus, the instantaneous voltage across a wave digital element can be calculated by the equation:

$$v(t) = \frac{a(t) + b(t)}{2} \quad (2.6)$$

Chapter 3

Methodology

3.1 Deriving Wave Digital elements

The simplest set of wave digital elements is the algebraic one ports. This is because there is only one port of Kirchoff domain behavior to account for, and because discretization is not necessary for algebraic elements.

3.1.1 Algebraic One Port Wave Digital Filters

Resistor

The resistor is the simplest wave digital element, as its behavior is described entirely by Ohm's law:

$$v(t) = i(t)R \tag{3.1}$$

In converting this to the wave digital domain via equation 2.6, we get the following relationship between the reflected and incident waves:¹

$$b(t) = a \frac{R - R_p}{R + R_p} \tag{3.2}$$

¹This equation holds in discrete time as there is no need to discretize algebraic elements, simply replace (t) indices by [n]

We can see that the resistor's reflected wave depends instantaneously on its incident wave, which constitutes a delay free loop. However, this can be solved by using our free variable port resistance. By setting the port resistance equal to the physical resistance, the right side of the equation reduces to 0 and eliminates the delay free loop. As a result, the adapted resistor's reflected wave is always 0.

Ideal voltage source

An ideal voltage source outputs a voltage $e(t)$ across its one port, i.e:

$$v(t) = e(t) \quad (3.3)$$

Replacing $v(t)$ with the wave digital definition of voltage, and solving for the reflected wave yields the relationship:

$$b(t) = 2R_p e(t) - a(t) \quad (3.4)$$

Again we have another delay free loop, however here there is no way to use the port resistance parameter to eliminate it. Thus, we can only use an ideal voltage source at the root of a connection tree, and not as a leaf node.

Ideal current source

An ideal current source outputs a current $j(t)$ across its one port, i.e:

$$i(t) = -j(t) \quad (3.5)$$

Replacing $j[t]$ with the wave digital definition of voltage, and solving for the reflected wave yields the relationship:

$$b(t) = 2R_p j(t) + a(t) \quad (3.6)$$

As was the case with the ideal voltage source, we have a deal free loop that cannot

be adapted with our port resistance parameter. Therefore ideal current sources also cannot be used as leaf nodes, and solely work at the root of a binary connection tree.

Resistive voltage source

A resistive voltage source is essentially an ideal voltage source in series with a resistor. This behavior is given by Kirchoff's voltage law:

$$v(t) - e(t) = Ri(t) \quad (3.7)$$

Replacing $v(t)$ with the wave digital definition of voltage, and solving for the reflected wave yields the wave-domain relationship:

$$b(t) = \frac{R - R_p}{R + R_p}a(t) + \frac{2R_p}{R + R_p}e(t) \quad (3.8)$$

In order to eliminate the delay free loop here to be able to use the resistive voltage source as a leaf node, we must set $R_p = R$ to make the coefficient $\frac{R-R_p}{R+R_p}$ equal to 0. The resulting adapted equation for the resistive voltage source's reflected wave is then:

$$b(t) = R_p e(t) \quad (3.9)$$

Resistive current source

The resistive current source can be described as an ideal current source in parallel with a resistor, and its behavior given by Kirchoff's current law:

$$j(t) + i(t) = \frac{v}{R_p} \quad (3.10)$$

Replacing $j(t)$ with the wave digital definition of voltage, and solving for the reflected

wave yields the relationship:

$$b(t) = \frac{R - R_p}{R + R_p}a(t) + \frac{2R_p}{R + R_p}j(t) \quad (3.11)$$

The delay free loop present can be eliminated by setting the coefficient $\frac{R-R_p}{R+R_p}$ equal to 0 by making $R_p = R$.

Short circuit

Ideally, a short circuit will have port voltage zero, i.e:

$$v(t) = 0 \quad (3.12)$$

In replacing the wave digital equation for voltage and solving for b , we get the following relation:

$$b(t) = -a(t) \quad (3.13)$$

As the port resistance parameter can not be used to break up the delay free loop present here, the short circuit is unadaptable and cannot be used as a leaf node.

Open circuit

Ideally, an open circuit will have port current zero, i.e:

$$i(t) = 0 \quad (3.14)$$

Replacing $i(t)$ with its wave digital definition and solving for its reflected wave, we find:

$$b(t) = a(t) \quad (3.15)$$

As was the case with the short circuit, the open circuit's reflected wave depends instantaneously on the value of its incident wave, which we cannot adapt with a

port resistance parameter. Thus the open circuit may only be used as a root node as well.

Switch

Short circuits and open circuits are essentially two components of a switch, and their equations may be combined to describe the behavior of a switch in the wave domain:

$$b(t) = \lambda a(t) \quad (3.16)$$

Where $\lambda = 1$ for an open switch and -1 for a closed switch. Again the switch cannot be adapted and may only be used at the root of a binary connection tree.

3.1.2 Reactive One Port Wave Digital Filters

Capacitor

The port behavior of a capacitor is modeled by the differential equation:

$$i(t) = C \frac{dv(t)}{dt} \quad (3.17)$$

Where $C = \text{Capacitance}$. In the Laplace domain, equation 3.17 looks like:

$$CsV(s) = I(s) \quad (3.18)$$

As Kirchoff's laws hold in the Laplace domain, we can insert our wave domain definitions of voltage and current into the Laplace domain equation. Once doing so, and solving for the reflected wave variable, we find the following transfer function:

$$H(s) = \frac{B(s)}{A(s)} = \frac{1 - R_p C s}{1 + R_p C s} \quad (3.19)$$

As the capacitor is reactive, its transfer function must be discretized. We will just consider the standard bilinear transform conformal mapping for discretization,

though others have been employed in the context of wave digital filters, such as the forwards & backwards Euler transforms, the alpha transform(s), and the möbius transform(s) [13]. The mapping from the Laplace s -plane to the z -plane by the bilinear transform is described by:

$$s \leftarrow \frac{2}{T} \frac{z-1}{z+1} \quad (3.20)$$

After employing the bilinear transform to the continuous time transfer function, we get a discrete time transfer function in the z -plane, to which we can apply the inverse z -transform to find the unadapted discrete time wave domain equation:

$$b[n] = -\frac{T-2R_pC}{T+2R_pC}b[n-1] + \frac{T-2R_pC}{T+2R_pC}a[n] + a[n-1] \quad (3.21)$$

By setting the free port resistance variable equal to $\frac{T}{2}C$, we will nullify the coefficients $\pm \frac{T-2R_pC}{T+2R_pC}$ and yield the adapted equation for the reflected wave:

$$b[t] = a[n-1] \quad (3.22)$$

Oddly, the result when using the bilinear transform to discretize a capacitor gives a reflected wave that is simply a unit delayed version of the incident wave.

Inductor

An inductor's behavior is described by the differential equation:

$$v(t) = L \frac{di(t)}{dt} \quad (3.23)$$

Where L = Inductance. In the Laplace domain, the inductor's equation is:

$$V(s) = LsI(s) \quad (3.24)$$

Placing our wave variable definitions of voltage and current into the Laplace domain equation gives us the transfer function:

$$H(s) = \frac{B(s)}{A(s)} = \frac{Ls - R_p}{Ls + R_p} \quad (3.25)$$

Like the capacitor, the inductor is reactive and must be discretized, we will again use the bilinear transform. Following discretization, we take the z -transform of the result and find the inductor's unadapted discrete time wave domain equation:

$$b[n] = \frac{2L - R_p T}{2L + R_p T} b[n - 1] + \frac{2L - R_p T}{2L + R_p T} a[n] - a[n - 1] \quad (3.26)$$

By setting the port resistance parameter equal to $\frac{2L}{T}$, we can cancel out the delay free loops and get the adapted equation:

$$b[n] = -a[n - 1] \quad (3.27)$$

As the capacitor and inductor are duals of one another, it should come as no surprise that the reflected wave equation of the inductor is simply the sign inverted version of the capacitor's wave equation.

3.1.3 Adaptors

The most common wave digital elements are the three port adaptors, specifically those for series and parallel connections. This is because ladder and lattice circuit topologies can be broken down entirely to series of parallel and or series connections. These are not the only types of adaptors, as behavior has been generalized for N -port adaptors, and the recently developed R -type adaptors are also very important. However, these adaptors are not necessary for our diode clipper and we will simply focus on the three-port series and parallel connections in this work.

Parallel Adaptor

The behavior of a three port parrallel connection with ports 0, 1, and 2 is described by the Kirchoff domain equations:

$$i_0 = i_1 = i_2 \quad (3.28)$$

$$v_0 + v_1 + v_2 = 0 \quad (3.29)$$

The behavior of multi port wave digital filters is generally described using linear algebra, so this equation rewritten in matrix form is:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_0 \\ v_1 \\ v_2 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i_0 \\ i_1 \\ i_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.30)$$

When replacing the voltage and current values with their wave digital definitions and solve for the reflected wave in matrix form, we find the following unadapted relationship:

$$\begin{bmatrix} b_0 \\ b_1 \\ b_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{R_{p0}R_{p1}+R_{p0}R_{p2}-R_{p1}R_{p2}}{R_{p0}R_{p1}+R_{p0}R_{p2}+R_{p1}R_{p2}} & \frac{2R_{p0}R_{p1}R_{p2}}{R_{p0}R_{p1}+R_{p0}R_{p2}+R_{p1}R_{p2}} & \frac{2R_{p0}R_{p1}R_{p2}}{R_{p0}R_{p1}+R_{p0}R_{p2}+R_{p1}R_{p2}} \\ \frac{2R_{p0}R_{p1}}{R_{p0}R_{p1}+R_{p0}R_{p2}+R_{p1}R_{p2}} & -\frac{2R_{p0}R_{p1}-R_{p0}R_{p2}+R_{p1}R_{p2}}{R_{p0}R_{p1}+R_{p0}R_{p2}+R_{p1}R_{p2}} & \frac{2R_{p0}R_{p1}R_{p2}}{R_{p0}R_{p1}+R_{p0}R_{p2}+R_{p1}R_{p2}} \\ \frac{2R_{p0}R_{p1}R_{p2}}{R_{p0}R_{p1}+R_{p0}R_{p2}+R_{p1}R_{p2}} & \frac{2R_{p0}R_{p1}R_{p2}}{R_{p0}R_{p1}+R_{p0}R_{p2}+R_{p1}R_{p2}} & -\frac{-R_{p0}R_{p1}+R_{p0}R_{p2}+R_{p1}R_{p2}}{R_{p0}R_{p1}+R_{p0}R_{p2}+R_{p1}R_{p2}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a_0 \\ a_1 \\ a_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.31)$$

If we want to adapt port 0, we can set its port resistance equal to $\frac{1}{1/R_{p1}+1/R_{p2}}$, yielding the adapted scattering matrix

$$\begin{bmatrix} b_0 \\ b_1 \\ b_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{R_{p2}}{(R_{p1}+R_{p2})} & \frac{R_{p1}}{(R_{p1}+R_{p2})} \\ \frac{R_{p2}}{(R_{p1}+R_{p2})} & -\frac{R_{p1}}{R_{p1}+R_{p2}} & \frac{R_{p1}R_{p2}}{R_{p1}+R_{p2}} \\ \frac{R_{p1}}{(R_{p1}+R_{p2})} & \frac{R_{p1}R_{p2}}{R_{p1}+R_{p2}} & -\frac{R_{p2}}{R_{p1}+R_{p2}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a_0 \\ a_1 \\ a_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.32)$$

We see that the adaptation criteria uses the inverse of the sum of the other two inverse port resistances, values that are also known as the port's conductance (G). An equivalent way to adapt port 0 is by setting its $G_0 = G_1 + G_2$. This holds for ports 1 and 2 as well, namely port 1 can be adapted by setting $G_1 = G_0 + G_2$, and port 2 by $G_2 = G_0 + G_1$.

Series Adaptor

Like the three-port parallel adaptor, the three-port series adaptor is also defined by a pair of Kirchoff domain equations:

$$v_0 = v_1 = v_2 \quad (3.33)$$

$$i_0 + i_1 + i_2 = 0 \quad (3.34)$$

Which, written in matrix form are as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_0 \\ v_1 \\ v_2 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} i_0 \\ i_1 \\ i_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.35)$$

Replacing the voltage and current variables with their definitions in the wave domain gives us the unadapted scattering matrix:

$$\begin{bmatrix} b_0 \\ b_1 \\ b_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{-R_{p0}+R_{p1}+R_{p2}}{R_{p0}+R_{p1}+R_{p2}} & -\frac{2R_{p0}R_{p1}}{R_{p0}+R_{p1}+R_{p2}} & -\frac{R_{p0}R_{p2}}{R_{p0}+R_{p1}+R_{p2}} \\ -\frac{2R_{p0}R_{p1}}{R_{p0}+R_{p1}+R_{p2}} & \frac{R_{p0}-R_{p1}+R_{p2}}{R_{p0}+R_{p1}+R_{p2}} & -\frac{2R_{p1}R_{p2}}{R_{p0}+R_{p1}+R_{p2}} \\ -\frac{2R_{p0}R_{p2}}{R_{p0}+R_{p1}+R_{p2}} & -\frac{2R_{p1}R_{p2}}{R_{p0}+R_{p1}+R_{p2}} & \frac{R_{p0}+R_{p1}-R_{p2}}{R_{p0}+R_{p1}+R_{p2}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a_0 \\ a_1 \\ a_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.36)$$

To adapt port 0, we can set its port resistance value R_{p0} equal to $R_{p1} + R_{p2}$, and find the adapted matrix:

$$\begin{bmatrix} b_0 \\ b_1 \\ b_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\frac{R_{p1}}{(R_{p1}+R_{p2})} & -\frac{R_{p2}}{(R_{p1}+R_{p2})} \\ -\frac{R_{p1}}{(R_{p1}+R_{p2})} & \frac{R_{p2}}{R_{p1}+R_{p2}} & \frac{R_{p1}R_{p2}}{R_{p1}+R_{p2}} \\ -\frac{R_{p2}}{(R_{p1}+R_{p2})} & -\frac{R_{p1}R_{p2}}{R_{p1}+R_{p2}} & \frac{R_{p1}}{R_{p1}+R_{p2}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} a_0 \\ a_1 \\ a_2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3.37)$$

Likewise, port 1 can be adapted by setting $R_{p1} = R_{p0} + R_{p2}$, and port 2 by setting $R_{p2} = R_{p0} + R_{p1}$.

3.1.4 Diode

As it is a nonlinear component, the diode cannot be adapted and can only be placed at the root of a connection tree. It must also be the circuit's lone nonlinear element.² Calculating the diode's behavior is significantly more involved than previous elements. We use herein the derivation of the reflected wave equation for a single diode, and a variable number of anti-parallel diodes in series published in [15]. The reflected wave equation derived by Werner et al. used in our diode pair in the Diode clipper circuit is as follows:

$$b = a - 2\lambda V_T \left[\mathcal{W} \left(\frac{RI_s}{V_T} e^{\frac{\lambda a}{V_T}} \right) + \mathcal{W} \left(-\frac{RI_s}{V_T} e^{-\frac{\lambda a}{V_T}} \right) \right] \quad (3.38)$$

Where a = the diode pair's incident wave, $\lambda = \text{signum}(a)$, V_t = thermal voltage, \mathcal{W} = the Lambert W function, R = port resistance, I_s = reverse bias saturation current.

The thermal voltage is computed by the number of anti-parallel diodes connected in series, so this equation allows us to vary the number of diodes used in the circuit.

² R -type adaptors allow for multiple nonlinearities, but are not utilized in this thesis.

3.2 Constructing Diode Clipper Wave Digital Circuit

To begin work on the project, we set out to construct a Python library³ of wave digital elements in order to build and run circuits with these components. We initially considered building the library in C++ to facilitate use in audio plugins, however there already exist a number of wave digital filter libraries in C++, while none are available in Python[16, 17]. We also feel that a library of wave digital filters in a language as accessible as Python greatly facilitate the process of prototyping wave digital circuits.

We follow an object oriented paradigm to construct the library, based on the work done by Chowdhury in [16]. We begin with the base one port object from which all wave digital elements will inherit. As noted earlier, all wave digital elements have incident and reflected waves, denoted by the variables a and b , thus these will be initialized to 0 upon creation of a wave digital element. The baseWDF class also has a number of methods available to each wave digital element, such as functionality to connect an element to its parent element in the binary connection tree derived from the original circuit. Additionally, there is a function to propagate a change of impedance to the rest of the tree should any parameter value of the circuit change, as well as a method for computing the voltage across a wave digital element. Lastly, a method to reset each element is included that returns all incident and reflected wave variables to 0.

The next object is the rootWDF, which inherits from the baseWDF but overwrites the functionality to connect an element to a parent and throws an error should this be attempted.

All of the one port objects and adaptors described in section 3.1 are straightforwardly constructed using these basic functionalities with their respective differences in determining their port resistance and reflected wave values, and whether they

³Publicly available at <https://github.com/gusanthon/diode-clipper-wdf>

Figure 1: Diode clipper schematic, with low pass filter highlighted

should inherit from the base (adaptable) class or the root (unadaptable) class.

One thing we must account for is solving the diode pair's reflected wave equation (3.38) at audio rates. The Lambert W function is quite costly to compute numerically and is unsatisfactory for real time applications. However, recent work published on the topic by D'Angelo et al. in [18] has found an accurate approximation of the function's solutions that can allow for real time use which we will employ.

The diode clipper works by cutting off both half cycles ⁴ of a sinusoid when its voltage level is above a certain threshold, which generally varies from diode to diode but is typically around ± 0.7 V. This behavior is illustrated in figure 2. Distortion circuits that include a diode clipper will often include an amplifying stage prior to the clipping stage, so that more of the input signal is above the clipping threshold and resulting in harder harmonic distortion.

The schematic we follow for the diode clipper circuit can be seen in figure 1. The parallel combination of the resistor and the capacitor highlighted acts as a passive low pass filter, the cutoff of which we can control by varying the resistance of R1. The resistance for a given cutoff value is calculated by equation 3.39, where C is the capacitor's capacitance in Farads.

⁴Both positive and negative half cycles are clipped with two anti-parallel diodes, a single diode will clip either the positive or negative half cycle depending on its orientation

Figure 2: Clipping both half cycles of a sinusoidal input with the diode clipper [19]

Figure 3: Diode clipper binary connection tree

This circuit's binary connection tree can be seen in figure 3. Because it is a nonlinear component, the diode pair is at the root of the tree. The next element in the tree is the parallel adaptor, denoted by the two parallel vertical lines. This adaptor connects its two child elements, the resistive voltage source and the capacitor in parallel. In practice, we represent the resistive voltage source as a series combination of a resistive voltage source with minimal resistance, and a resistor that we use to control the cutoff of the low pass filter.

Also included of course are functions to set each of the parameters of the circuit like filter cutoff, input gain and output gain, as well as the option to specify the number of diodes used in the circuit.

$$R = \frac{1}{2\pi C \cdot \text{cutoff}} \quad (3.39)$$

To build the Diode Clipper wave digital filter circuit, we construct a DiodeClipper class in which we initialize each of the components and necessary connections. In order to use it to process any audio inputs, we can run a for loop, in which we set the input voltage of the circuit, and set it in motion by having the root element accept the next element's reflected wave as an incident wave, followed by the next element accepting the root element's reflected wave as an incident wave. Because these methods recursively call parent elements' incident and reflected wave equations, the circuit has completed a cycle once they finish running, and we can then probe the voltage for the system's output at the current iteration. We can place this behavior in a member function to process an individual sample.

Plot_freqz is another member function that processes the circuit with a Dirac delta function to obtain the system's impulse response with its current parameters, and subsequently visualize its magnitude and phase responses with the matplotlib library.

We have further included methods for circuits to process audio in real time using the pyaudio interface, and are able to achieve performance suitable for recording (latency ≈ 10 ms) at higher sample rates.

3.3 Evaluation Methods

First we will compare the frequency response across several parameter changes and sample rates. We test the circuit at the cutoff values:

$$\{70, 150, 250, 500, 1000, 2000, 4000, 8000, 16000\}\text{Hz}. \quad (3.40)$$

Across sample rates of:

$$\{44100, 48000, 882000, 96000\}\text{Hz}. \quad (3.41)$$

In order to verify that the clipper circuit is behaving correctly, we must compare it to the true behavior of a diode clipper circuit. For this work, we treat the outputs

of LTSpice circuit simulations as the ground truth.

For a rigorous analysis, we will make comparisons between the wave digital diode clipper and the Spice simulation across several parameter values at different sample rates. We take note of the differences between the observed and predicted values and compute the error between them.

Error metrics

We use the following metrics to determine error between the predicted and observed values.

Mean squared error:

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - \hat{Y}_i)^2 \quad (3.42)$$

Error to signal ratio:

$$\text{ESR} = \frac{\sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} |y_p[n] - \hat{y}_p[n]|^2}{\sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} |y_p[n]|^2} \quad (3.43)$$

We will next account for the nonlinear behavior of the diode clipper by performing a transient analysis, in which we process sine waves and examine the system's output. Specifically, we will look at the amount of total harmonic distortion plus noise (THD+N%, defined in eq. 3.44) that is introduced to the system as we increase the input gain parameter to clip the signal harder.

$$\text{THD} + N(\%) = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} (V_N^2) + V_{NOISE}^2}}{V_1} \times 100 \quad (3.44)$$

We will lastly evaluate the system using the swept sine method presented by Angelo Farina in [8]. This technique is a powerful tool for examining nonlinear systems such as the diode clipper. It consists of taking the output of feeding an exponentially swept sine wave across all frequencies below Nyquist into a nonlinear system.

The swept sine is defined as:

$$x[n] = A \sin \left(\omega_1 T_R \left[e^{\left\{ \frac{n}{T_R} \right\}} - 1 \right] \right) \quad (3.45)$$

Where T_R is defined as:

$$T_R = \frac{N}{\ln \left(\frac{\omega_2}{\omega_1} \right)} \quad (3.46)$$

In which N refers to the length of the sweep in samples, ω_1 refers to the starting frequency of the sweep, and ω_2 is the end frequency. The processed sweep is then convolved with an inverse filter⁵ of the input sweep, which creates a multi-dimensional impulse response. This shows the behavior of the system at different harmonics, and is analogous to the Volterra Series (eq. 2.3). The processed sine sweep divided by the input sweep is the transfer function that describes the system in its entirety. [20]

We propose a metric for evaluating the contribution of noise from each harmonic, the Harmonic to Signal Ratio (HSR). It is similar to the Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR) (equation 3.47 [21]), but differs in that we are treating the upper harmonics' magnitude responses as the noisy signal(s) compared to the fundamental. We calculate this by computing the difference of the magnitude response of each harmonic and the of the fundamental frequency's magnitude response. The equation for the i th harmonic's HSR is shown in 3.48.

$$\text{SNR}_{\text{dB}} = 10 \log_{10} \left[\left(\frac{A_{\text{signal}}}{A_{\text{noise}}} \right)^2 \right] = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{A_{\text{signal}}}{A_{\text{noise}}} \right) = 2 (A_{\text{signal, dB}} - A_{\text{noise, dB}}) \quad (3.47)$$

$$\text{HSR}_{\text{dB}_i} = 2(20 \log_{10}(H_i) - (20 \log_{10}(H_0))) \quad (3.48)$$

⁵The inverse filter amounts to a time reversed and amplitude modulated version of the original sweep

Chapter 4

Results

4.1 Frequency Response Evaluation

Table 4.1 shows the average mean squared error for the magnitude and phase, averaged across all cutoff parameters at different sample rates. Table 4.1 makes the same comparison but shows the error to signal ratio.

In figure 4 we show the magnitude response of the wave digital filter plotted against the magnitude response of the LTSpice simulation, with the input gain at 0 dB and the cutoff at 1000 hz, sampled at 44.1 khz. Figure 5 shows the phase response comparison at the same parameters. For reference, the mean squared error of the the magnitude response in figure 4 is 7.4475 dB, which is slightly higher than the overall average, while the mean squared error of the phase response in figure 5 is $1.877 * 10^{-5}$ radians, which is slightly lower than the overall average.

We can also see from these figures that the plots really only begin to deviate as they approach the Nyquist frequency, at which the behavior of the digital circuit is undefined.

Although of course evaluating the frequency response amounts to evaluating the LTI behavior of the system, and fails to account for any nonlinear behavior.

Figure 4: Magnitude response WDF vs Spice at 44.1 khz

Figure 5: Phase response WDF vs Spice at 44.1 khz

Sample Rate	Magnitude ESR [dB]	Phase ESR [rad]
44.1khz	1.703	0.0185
48khz	1.324	0.0149
88.2khz	0.416	0.003
96khz	0.344	0.0028

Table 1: Avg. ESR of magnitude and phase across all parameter changes by sample rate

Sample Rate	Magnitude MSE [dB]	Phase MSE [rad.]
44.1khz	7.215	0.001
48khz	6.837	0.015
88.2khz	7.035	0.003
96khz	6.660	0.003

Table 2: Avg. MSE of magnitude and phase across all parameter changes by sample rate

4.2 Transient Analysis

We show in table 3 the results of the measurements from processing a 1khz sine wave at a sample rate of 44.1khz, with the cutoff parameter at 1khz. We observed very little variation in the THD+N calculations when varying the sample rate and the cutoff parameter.

Input gain [dB]	THD+N [%]
-20	0.01708
-15	0.01743
-10	0.02869
-5	0.437
0	6.89743
5	15.51905
10	21.85888
15	26.42446
20	29.61084
25	31.97835
30	33.5589
35	35.05479
40	37.11475
45	38.30848

Table 3: THD+N% introduced at each input gain value, $f_s = 44100$, $\text{cutoff} = 1000$

An interesting note is that at even negative input gain values, there still appears

Figure 6: Output spectrum of 1kHz sine wave processed by clipper at 44.1kHz sample rate

Figure 7: Output waveforms at different input gains

Figure 8: Spectrogram of log sweep sine input

some harmonic distortion. This indicates that the nonlinearity is still contributing to the output even when the input is not crossing the clipping threshold.

Figure 7 shows how increasing the input gain parameter contributes to the 'squaring' of the input waveform.

The frequency spectrum of the output waveform processed by the diode clipper at a sample rate of 44.1kHz, with a cutoff of 1000 hz and 15 dB of input gain can be seen in figure 6, clearly showing the odd harmonics added to the pure sine tone by the system.

4.3 Swept Sine Method

A spectrogram of the sine sweep input is shown in 8, and the output spectrogram is shown in 9 which are used to generate the complete transfer function.

We show the multidimensional impulse response generated from this method in figure 10. Each vertical line corresponds with the systems impulse response at increasing harmonic. We can then compute the FFT of each of these impulse responses to

Figure 9: Spectrogram of log sweep sine output

Figure 10: Diode clipper circuit multi dimensional impulse response

Figure 11: Each harmonic's magnitude response

understand the magnitude and phase response at each of the individual harmonics. We show the magnitude responses of the first 9 harmonics of the diode clipper at default parameters in figure 11. The fundamental's magnitude response (harmonic #1) is essentially an alias of the signal, as we can see it is fairly consistent in energy between 20 hz and 20 khz, with a slight taper as it approaches Nyquist due to the low pass filter in the circuit.

The measurements of each harmonic's Harmonic to Signal Ratio can be seen in table 4. The HSR of the first (fundamental) harmonic is of course 0 dB as it is being compared to itself. Each successive harmonic's HSR is greater than its previous, as the distance between the harmonic and the fundamental increases as the harmonic increases.

Harmonic #	Harmonic to signal ratio [dB]
1	0
2	34.63
3	60.51
4	73.69
5	81.27
6	91.58
7	101.77
8	108.91
9	115.14

Table 4: Each harmonic's Harmonic to Signal Ratio (HSR)

Chapter 5

Discussion

5.1 Discussion

In this work, we have aimed to demonstrate how effective the virtual analog modeling method of wave digital filters is. We have shown that it can accurately simulate the outputs of traditional linear time invariant passive low pass filters, as well as capture the nonlinear behavior of systems like the diode clipper. We have shown that the results are stable and consistent across parameter changes and different sample rates.

Although the original limitations of the wave digital filter formalism placed significant constraints on the types of circuits that can be realized, continued developments are changing this. Indeed, complex circuit topologies may be difficult to decompose into connection trees, though advancements from graph theory have led to algorithms to decompose a circuit netlist into a connection tree efficiently and automatically.

5.2 Future work

In our evaluation, we see that each increasing harmonic has a lower bandwidth than the previous. We also see some strange interference patterns occurring at approximately 1 khz. It would be interesting to investigate the exact causes of this

behavior and determine if it is a result of the sweep's behavior or the circuit itself.

The sine sweep analysis was only conducted on the circuit with its default parameters at 44.1 khz. Future work should make these same evaluations at additional parameter changes and sample rates and compare the behaviors. We would also like to gain a greater understanding of the phase responses of each harmonic, to combine with the magnitude responses for a fuller description of the system. Additionally, we would like to perform this analysis on other nonlinear circuits to gain more data for the Harmonic to Signal Ratio (HSR).

Further, this thesis has focused specifically on evaluating the the behavior of the nonlinearities of the diode clipper circuit. However, in the process of building this circuit, we constructed a python library capable of running many more classes of circuits.

The library includes all of the elements described in section 3.1, as well as the Diode Clipper class we created for this thesis. The repository further includes a working second order passive low pass filter.

In addition, we have included R -type adaptor classes, both adapted and unadapted that are functioning properly. The unadapted R -type class has been used in another circuit class emulating the TR-808 hi-hat resonator based on Werner's work in [13] and Chowdhury's work in [16].

We have also begun work on a generic Circuit class, from which any other wave digital circuit class may inherit. Generalized functions include setting the sample rate, which is done by ensuring that any stateful item used in the circuit is prepared with the correct sample rate, and that any parameters depending on a sample rate are recomputed with the new value. The generic circuit class also contains each of the functions used in the Diode Clipper circuit, such as such as processing an individual sample, processing entire signals, and functions to compute the system's impulse response, as well as plot its magnitude and phase responses.

Also included in the generic Circuit class is a function to record mono audio in real

time, allowing any child class access to this functionality. Thanks to the great efficiency of wave digital filters, this has been able to run with usable latency at audio rates even in a language as high level as python. Circuits which include *R*-type adaptors are considerably more costly to run in real time, though real time performance with them is still achievable. An additional way to optimize performance, especially that of *R*-type adaptors, would be to incorporate single instruction multiple data (SIMD) processing with the python simd library. [16] [22]

We believe that further expanding this library can be of great benefit to the community of virtual analog developers. We hope to include graph decomposition algorithms that can turn a net list into a connection tree, greatly simplifying the process of prototyping complicated circuits.

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